

Performance of High Fibre Volume Fraction (V_f) CFRP Under Exposure to High Energy Events

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Introduction

- CFRP is highly vulnerable to laser exposure due to poor:
 1. Thermal stability of matrix
 2. Thermal conductivity
 3. Fire retardance
 4. Reflectance/Absorbance

- Sparse open source literature on continuous wave laser ablation

30 mm Beam

10 mm Beam

High Fibre Volume Fraction (V_f) Composites

- Carbon fibres consume ~98% of the latent enthalpy of vapourisation compared to resin [1] [2]

⇒ V_f will influence ablation [3]

- To induce high V_f , dry and prepreg plies are combined and press cured – 16 total plies

Material ID	V_f Achieved	Stacking Pattern
V1	0.56	■ ■ ■ ■ ■
V2	0.67	■ ■ ▨ ■ ■
V3	0.71	■ ▨ ■ ▨ ■
V4	0.57	▨ ■ ▨ ■ ▨

■ Dry
 ▨ Prepreg

Example Stacking Sequence

- [1] Wolynski A. et al, *Effect of process strategies on thermal load during CFRP manufacturing using picosecond laser pulses*. International Congress on Applications of Lasers. (2010). 723-730.
- [2] Chen-Wu W. et al, *Ablation behaviors of carbon reinforced polymer composites by laser of different operation modes*. Optics & Laser Technology, 2015. 73: p. 23-28.
- [3] E. Oeltjen et al, *High-energy laser effects on carbon fiber reinforced polymer composites with a focus on perforation time*. Journal of Composite Materials, 2021. 55(16).

Experiments & Methodology

Laser Specs:

- 3760 Wcm⁻², 100 W, 1.75 mm
- Near-Infrared/ Continuous Wave

Variables measured:

1. Perforation Time (s)
2. Mass Ablation Rate (mg/s)
3. Linear Ablation Rate (μm/s)
4. Back-face Temperature (°C)

➤ Angle of incidence: 0°

➤ Perforation achieved when power meter registers >1 W

**Profilometry
of Ablation Pit**

Laser Perforation Testing

- V1-V3 → Clear Positive Trend
 - 48% increase in perforation time
 - 58% decrease in mass ablation rate
- V4 → Manufacturing defects cause drop in performance
- When normalised against density:
 - ⇒ 35% increase in perforation time

Laser Fixed Dwell Time Tests

Effect of Dwell Time

Ablation Pit Cross-sections

- Ablation Pit Narrows
- Larger Heat Affected Zone (HAZ) appears to fade but does not shrink

Front

Rear

Ablation Damage Zones by Area ^{*}@ ~500 W/cm², 10 s, 25 mm spot

**Concentric Circles of CFRP Laser
Damage Zones (not to scale)**

[1][2]	Label	Description	Diameter* (relative to beam)	Temp* (°C)
	Full Perforation	No Solid Matrix or Fibre, Some	0.95	~3500
	Semi-Perforation	Sporadic Fibre Remnants, Odd Spots of Char	1-1.3	~3500
	Heavy Ablation	Charred Resin, Protuberant Tapered Fibres, Significant Separation	1.6	1000- 3500
	Light Ablation	Semi-Charred Matrix, Near Virgin Fibres, Moderated Separation	1.6-2	400-1000
	Heat Affected Zone	Mechanical Losses, Minor Separation	2	150-400
	Virgin Region	Not affected	N/A	<150

Ablation Pit Edge

- Between the Heavy Ablation and Semi-Perforation
- V3: sharp gradient of damage

4 Point Bending

- Conducted under ASTM D6272 with 128 mm support span
- Virgin coupons tested against ablated

Failure Mechanism:

- Virgin → Abrupt delamination/fibre breakage
- Ablated → Gradual matrix cracking

Virgin

Ablated

4 Point Bending Results

- V_f correlates with strength
- V1-V3 → ~50% drop in strength
- Strength loss unaffected by V_f
 - This supports that the HAZ is the same size for all, and is the determinant
- Decrease in mass ablation rate → less material (resin) removed

Damage to 4 Point Bending Samples

- Following strength loss, would expect ~50% damage coverage
- However, visible ablation damage has <50% coverage
- Therefore, heat affected zone must extend beyond visible damage

One more thing... Variable Through-Thickness V_f (VV)

- High V_f Front, Low V_f Rear \Rightarrow Functional Grading

Summary

- Clear trends between ablation behaviour and V_f
- Fibres protect underlying resin – achieved over time and with high V_f
- V_f does not affect drops in flexural strength post-ablation
- Press curing has a V_f limit after which properties reduce

Thanks for
listening
Any Questions?

